

Project: 101108469 — PreMETS — ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO

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PreMETS

Predictive Maintenance Education & Training System: An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

Project Acronym: **PreMETS**

Project Title: **Predictive Maintenance Education & Training System: An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training**

Project Number: **101108469**

Topic: **ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO-EDU-ENTERP**

Type of Action: **ERASMUS-LS**

D5.2 WBL Pilot 2

Final

Deliverable:	WBL Pilot 2
Work Package:	WP5
Due Date:	30/09/2025
Submission Date:	29/09/2025
Start Date of Project:	01/07/2023
Duration of Project:	36 months
Organisation Responsible of Deliverable:	UPRC
Version:	1.3
Status:	Final
Author name(s):	Christos Nedeloglou
Reviewer(s):	Afroditi Anagnostopoulou
Nature:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R – Report P – Prototype D – Demonstrator O - Other
Dissemination level:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU – Public CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission) RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history			
Version	Date	Modified by (author/partner)	Comments
1.1	15/09/2025	Christos Nedeloglou (UPRC)	Completed
1.2	26/09/2025	Afroditi Anagnostopoulou (CERTH)	Minor Revisions
1.3	29/09/2025	Ioannis Ergas (WEGEMT)	Acceptance

Table of Contents

Contents

<i>Executive Summary</i>	5
1. <i>Introduction</i>	7
2. <i>Pilot design and methodology</i>	7
3. <i>Participant profiles</i>	8
3.1 <i>Learners & Mentors/Trainers</i>	8
3.2 <i>Partners</i>	9
4. <i>Training and learning components</i>	10
4.1 <i>Initial recruitment of our participants</i>	11
4.2 <i>Virtual Learning through the Platform</i>	11
4.3 <i>On-site visit to PCT (Piraeus Container Terminal)</i>	12
4.4 <i>Mentorship and other activities</i>	13
5. <i>Outcomes and certification</i>	13
6. <i>Stakeholders' collaboration</i>	14
7. <i>Evaluation</i>	15
8. <i>Annex A: Photos from the on-site visit to PCT</i>	19

Abbreviations and Terminology

Abbreviations	
EQAB	External Quality Assurance Board
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PCT	Piraeus Container Terminal
PM	Predictive Maintenance
QuALS	Quantitative Analysis in Shipping Laboratory
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
TIF	Thessaloniki International Fair
VET	Vocational and Educational Training
WBL	Work-based Learning

Terminology	
Cross-disciplinary learning	Learning activities which overlap across disciplines but remain connected by a single shared subject, i.e. Predictive Maintenance.
Micro-credentials	Certification for short, focused courses.
Teaching Factory concept	A collaborative educational model that simulates a real-world production environment within a school or university to provide students with hands-on, practical experience in manufacturing, services, and other industries.
Work-based learning	An educational strategy that integrates the classroom with the real workplace to provide students with practical skills, knowledge, and career experience

Executive Summary

This report presents the design, implementation, and outcomes of the Work-Based Learning (WBL) Pilot 2 in Piraeus, Greece, which focused on PM applications in the maritime sector. It assesses the effectiveness of the pilot, especially with regards to the collaboration, learning and impact on both the learners, trainers and stakeholders involved. The report presents the background of the pilot that was implemented and its linkage to the wider objectives of the PreMETS project, where essentially they served as the testing ground for the material and the platform that were previously created. Next, it presents the Work-Based Learning (WBL) framework methodology on which it is based, followed by the profiles of the participants and their mentors/trainers. The next section breaks down the training and learning components in detail, followed by the outcomes of the pilot, the collaboration between stakeholders and its evaluation based on the PreMETS project's Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

The PreMETS project, in general, addresses a critical skills gap in Predictive Maintenance (PM), a field essential for optimizing infrastructure, reducing resource use, and supporting Europe's digital and green transition. Recognizing the lack of comprehensive PM curricula, PreMETS set out to create an integrated learning ecosystem combining innovative educational tools, digital resources, and industry collaboration. Its five objectives span from the creation of cross-disciplinary learning and training toolkits, to the development of a digital platform and micro-credentialing, culminating in piloting work-based learning schemes that blend theory with hands-on industry experience. This pilot aimed to address its last objective, i.e. piloting the training courses and the platform, as well as expanding the knowledge gained by the learners through their visit in physical settings of maritime operations, based on a blended-teaching methodology.

Over three months, 25 participants—mainly university students in maritime studies and mechanical engineering, alongside VET learners and industry employees—engaged in a blended learning and training program combining online modules available through the digital platform of the project, a physical visit at the Piraeus Container Terminal, and mentorship from local and international experts both in guidance and in activities, such as an entrepreneurial challenge to link PM knowledge with real business challenges as they were presented by industry professionals.

Key achievements include:

- Successful certification of all 25 learners through micro-credentials, equipping them with technical, analytical, and problem-solving skills relevant to Industry 4.0.
- Practical exposure to maritime operations, bridging the gap between theory and real-world application of PM, particularly in critical port infrastructure.
- Positive learner feedback on the platform's flexibility, accessibility, and efficiency, especially for participants that had to balance their studies or their job schedules.
- Strengthened consortium collaboration, involving academic institutions, VET providers, SMEs, and European-level associations, ensuring high-quality delivery and scalability.

- Sectoral impact, with maritime stakeholders highlighting PM's potential to improve safety, efficiency, and environmental performance—key EU Green Deal and Digital Agenda priorities.

The pilot demonstrated the effectiveness of PreMETS's blended methodology and confirmed the value of PM-focused micro-credentials in enhancing employability and upskilling both for students and professionals. By aligning education with real industrial challenges and EU strategic objectives, PreMETS provides a model for sustainable, scalable workforce development in predictive maintenance across multiple sectors. The effective cooperation between the partners of the project and the collaboration with external stakeholders, such as the private and the public sector ensured that the pilot phase of PreMETS succeeded in achieving its purpose and met its assigned KPIs.

1. Introduction

Predictive Maintenance (PM) is a critical element for infrastructure systems and the efficient use of primary resources. The lack of a comprehensive PM curricula inspired the PreMETS project, which aims to spearhead the creation of an alliance to boost European Innovation in this domain with the cooperation of industry and education, in order to create a coherent digital platform that covers all the PM processes and allows for the training of VET learners, students and existing workforce and provide them with a micro-certification. In short, it consists of five objectives:

- OBJ1: Create a cross-disciplinary, cross-sectoral PM education toolkit for learners.
- OBJ2: Create a cutting-edge toolkit for trainers in the field of PM.
- OBJ3: Develop a micro-credential certification framework for micro-courses in PM.
- OBJ4: Develop a digital platform that entails the above, and a virtual space for blended Teaching Factories deployment.
- OBJ5: Pilot the training courses and the digital platform via innovative Work-Based learning (WBL) blended apprenticeship secondments with participants from academia, VET and industry (under the moderation of trainers and experts) to test their gained knowledge both in digital and physical settings.

Based on the work plan of the project, the Working Package 5 (WP5) is meant to pilot test the platform and, thus, the content and the tools created in previous work packages (WP2, WP3, and WP4), as well as to identify improvement opportunities and enhance its impact. The Work-Based Learning (WBL) Pilot 2 in Piraeus serves the purpose of going a step further in the project and narrowing down the sectoral scope of PM applications to maritime operations. Learners, in parallel or having already read the content of the project's curriculum in our digital platform, made the next essential step in vocational training – direct exposure to the actual working environment and physical settings, while also benefiting from the transfer of knowledge from professionals and experts in the field.

2. Pilot design and methodology

The Working Package 5 of the PreMETS project relates directly to the achievement of OBJ5 mentioned above (“Pilot the training courses and the platform”) and the following sub-objectives:

- Define the pedagogical methodology for blended work-based learning (in company + via the PreMETS platform);
- Recruit companies and trainees/apprentices for the PM pilots.
- Implement 2 pilots of 3 months each and identify learning opportunities/improvements for learners and trainers.

- Institutionalize the work-based learning framework in the education providers and industries' operations.

The WBL Pilot 2 followed the WBL blended methodology as described in T5.1 in Working Package 5 and according to OBJ5 of the project, based on which mixed learners from academia, VET and industry (under trainers' moderation) experimented the knowledge they gained on Predictive Maintenance both in digital and physical environments. Based on the EITM guidelines for a Teaching Factory Tool, the Blended Learning Approach consisted of:

- Online modules on the PreMETS platform.
- On-site activities and live demonstrations.
- Group discussions and mentor-led workshops.

The two pilots, consisting of 25 learners each, offered them the opportunity to learn about PM through the modules in the digital platform, and get certified through the micro-certification tool created for the project. As explained further below, the deployment of the digital platform as a learning tool is deemed important and truly successful for its efficiency and the flexibility it provides, particularly for the profile of the learners (students and VET learners seeking to upskill) that took part in our Work-Based Learning pilot in Greece.

The designated trainers, on the other hand, had the opportunity to initially receive training as trainers (also through the platform), experiment on the customization of the pilot, evaluate learners' progress through learner analytics, and engage in skill forecasting for the future.

Eventually, participants had the opportunity to not just stay with all the theoretical knowledge about PM through their online micro-courses, but also observe its application in real industrial settings – either in manufacturing or maritime transport environments, depending on which pilot they participated in. Adhering to the core purpose of the project as a whole, the pilot bridged the theoretical knowledge with a first step into a real working environment, which is often a hurdle for many students after graduating – or VET learners and workers who are having second thoughts on whether they should “break the ice” and look at what an emerging field like Predictive Maintenance looks like on the inside, before deciding if such a future career move suits their preferences.

3. Participant profiles

3.1 Learners & Mentors/Trainers

The main learner type of the WBL 2 pilot in Greece were 25 VET learners and higher education students from Greece, as per the project' requirements. In particular, the majority of learners were university students (17 out of 25 participants in total), with a background either in Maritime studies or Mechanical engineering at a graduate or at a postgraduate level. The rest of the participants were employees in companies operating in the logistics and maritime sectors. Gender-wise, the pilot achieved an almost perfect balance, with 13 female and 12 male

participants (there was no expressed demand from any of the participants to be identified under a different gender preference).

Mentors and trainers from the pre-pilot phase, both local (from CERTH, YET and ACC) and international (WEG, DB and EITM) were readily available for learners to reach them throughout the 3-month duration of the project via the PreMETS platform forum, and guide them in their learning process of their micro-courses in the digital platform and with potential questions that could arise.

3.2 Partners

The commitment of the Consortium to the successful implementation of the WBL pilot 2 stems both from their wider experience that rendered them suitable for the project, as well as the institutional added value they got in turn from the project, as each of them has a direct incentive/gain from this joint work.

Local partners:

- **CERTH** is a leading research center in Greece conducting specialized basic and applied research and offering high quality services in several fields. It is a non-profit private status legal entity supervised by the General Secretariat for Research and Technology (GSRT) of the Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs. CERTH is listed among the top 10 EU institutions with the highest participation in competitive research grants. CERTH, being the only research institute in Greece and South-eastern Europe with a dedicated structural and Infrastructure Research Lab specializing in Predictive Maintenance, has a strong interest in the development of robust PM training and educational systems. CERTH will apply the PreMETS platform outcome and programs across the wide network of affiliated industries and major infrastructure stakeholders in the region.
- **YET** is an adult and youth training centre from Greece with a track record of training 5000+ learners in fields related to digitalization, entrepreneurship and innovation by relying on their innovative tools. It is also an expert in accessing, including and training social groups at risk which is of high importance for PreMETS. YET, as a Member of the EU Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition and has grasped the importance of Tech skills and Digital Transformation in the current local and global startup, scale-up and business environment and thus has dedicated a series of activities to this field. Up to date, YET has contributed for the successful delivery of the PreMETS platform in WP4, that will be incorporated in their educational portfolio afterwards. Even more, YET's staff were keen to learn and implement the teaching factory concept from PreMETS (via EITM's efforts) and potentially examine how it can be transferred to other forms of (non-formal) education, which was exactly the methodology that was applied in the WBL Pilot 2 (likewise WBL Pilot 1).
- **ACC** is a Cyprus-based company (SME) recognised as a highly skilled business partner that helps its customers excel in the era of globalization, technology acceleration and climate change. It offers (among others) software development and business consulting services linked to IoT, Big Data/ AI and Cyber-Security technologies, including business modelling, business planning and techno-economic analysis services. As a technical company ACC has also extensive knowhow in predictive/predictive

manufacturing by being involved in several relative projects. ACC has been heavily involved in both content and pilot development to ensure the relevance of the outputs.

International partners:

- **WEG** (association registered in the Netherlands) is a European Association of the largest network of marine related universities in 16 European countries, formed in 1978 for increasing the knowledge base and updating and extending the skills of practicing engineers and postgraduate students working at an advanced level in marine technology (including predictive manufacturing) and related sciences. Due to its nature, the mission and the motives of WEG's participation in the project are clear: to co-create training content for their members (the PM content from PreMETS), to enlarge the partner base with new members (i.e. to launch invitations to PreMETS partners to join the WEG network) and to provide transnational networking opportunities for their members (i.e. via the PreMETS platform). WEG has contributed throughout the 3-month implementation of the pilot, always being available to provide guidance to learners via the platform.
- **DB** is an Italian Research and Consultancy SME specialized in Safety, Human Factors, Security and Validation. Deep Blue operates in the domain of Transportation dealing with the design, analysis and evaluation of interactive systems. DB has an extensive experience with design of tailored-made training courses with traditional training methods as well as innovative methodologies and techniques (such as e-learning, web-based training, blended learning, etc.). For this reason, DB is an excellent contributor to WP2 content and WP5 pilot coaching. Their know-how in coaching learners and successful PM solutions has been particularly useful for them, whenever asked by them through the platform.
- **EITM** (European level Institute) was established in 2019 by the EC with a vision that global manufacturing will continue to be led by Europe and contributing to make Europe and its manufacturing sector more competitive and sustainable. EITM's mission is to bring together Europe's manufacturing actors. In doing so, EIT Manufacturing brings together a growing network of top-tier industrial partners, leading academic and research institutions from across the region and innovative startups, scaleups and SMEs. EITM provides EU-wide education, capacity building and innovation-development platforms. Even more, the pilot phase as a whole – and particularly the two pilots that took place concurrently – has been of utmost interest for EITM, as they rely on EITM's teaching factory concept. Considering these, EITM have proved to be great mentors for the WP5 pilots – including WBL 2 Pilot - and a true enabler/leader of PreMETS's dissemination, communication and impact thus far, with the capacity to reach targeted industries at the EU level in the next steps of the project – and the final piece in this Working Package (WP5) too.

4. Training and learning components

The task of Work-Based Learning (WBL) Pilot 2 was led by the University of Piraeus Research Center (UPRC) with the aim of fulfilling Objective 5 of the PreMETS project as described above, focusing on the context of maritime transport operations.

WBL Pilot 2 was designed as a blended learning experience that combined digital, practical, and mentoring elements to give participants a comprehensive understanding of the maritime transport sector. The pilot began with **virtual learning sessions** delivered through the PreMETS platform, allowing participants to acquire foundational knowledge and engage with interactive materials at their own pace. This online component was followed by **on-site visits** to the targeted industry environment (in this case, the Piraeus container terminal) where participants observed real-world operations, interacted with industry professionals, and gained hands-on exposure to port activities and logistics processes. To further support participants' learning journeys, WBL Pilot 2 included a **structured mentorship component**, pairing learners with experienced trainers from both local and international contexts. This mentorship provided personalized guidance, encouraged reflection on experiences, and helped participants bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. Together, these elements created a well-rounded and immersive work-based learning experience tailored to the needs of the maritime transport sector.

4.1 Initial recruitment of our participants

The 25 participants of the pilot were initially recruited either through a presentation of the project and the pilot's objectives at the University of Piraeus, or through communication with PM-related companies in logistics and maritime transport for industry workers who wanted to upskill and expand their knowledge on the subject. For their virtual training, most learners completed their micro-courses and received their micro-certification during the designated three-month period of the pilot. As the majority of learners were university students and the third month of the pilot coincided with their university exams, it was decided (after communication with EQAB) to provide them an extension for the successful completion of the virtual training.

4.2 Virtual Learning through the Platform

The deployment and use of the PreMETS digital platform for the learning material developed in WP2 was a perfect fit for the learners' profile, as mentioned above for a number of reasons. As most of them belong to a "digital" generation of Europe, they are fully accustomed to such online learning tools, and they prefer it for its 24/7 availability – some like to study early, some late at night – and the efficiency that comes with it. In addition, most of our participants were students with varying schedules and demands for their university programs, with some having mid-term exams or semester exams in May and June. That translates into shifting their focus on their university exams for certain periods of time, yet the opportunity to log in the PreMETS platform whenever their obligations allowed for it meant unparalleled flexibility.

Some other participants of the WBL Pilot 2 were already working with a set job schedule – one that again might differ for some, e.g. one of them mentioned how his occupation at a logistics distribution center had a dynamic

rotation of shifts, therefore he would be working morning, afternoon and night shifts. The digital platform was perhaps the sole way for this participant to keep up with the necessary progress with the learning material to gain the micro-credential certification.

Eventually, all participants orally stated how satisfied they were with the use of the platform for the learning material due to the convenience, the time flexibility and the ease to handle it, as well as the efficiency in understanding predictive maintenance by having a number of learning means (e.g. explanatory and demonstrating videos related to the material provided to them). All the above contributed to them eventually gaining a micro-certification that they can put in their CV and use in the future in pursue of a job in a related field.

4.3 On-site visit to PCT (Piraeus Container Terminal)

The Quantitative Analysis in Shipping Laboratory (QuALS), representing the University of Piraeus, organized a visit to the Piraeus Container Terminal (PCT). During the visit, participants were given a tour around the port's facilities, with almost all of them enjoying the opportunity to see up-close the infrastructure and equipment used in container transport for the first time. During the tour, the basic operations were presented, as well as an insightful explanation of the maintenance procedures and the value that predictive maintenance can provide in such environments, where faults and trouble-shooting can be heavily burdensome – both in terms of costs and traffic bottlenecks, especially in the current settings where ports work up to the limits of their capacity due to the geopolitical instability that affects maritime supply chains.

The hosts were eager to respond to all the questions of the learners and mentors in the discussion that followed their tour and presentation, providing them with enlightening clarifications on their questions. It must be noted that photos were not allowed during the tour due to GDPR restrictions, except for the collective ones posted below. The tour was conducted with the use of a mini-bus for the security of the participants, the facilitation of movement (in case of mobility issues) and protection from extreme heat (the temperature in Athens that day was 42 degrees Celsius).

In essence, learners had the opportunity to come in touch with the industry for the first time and see in reality the facilities, conditions, and requirements that Predictive Maintenance has on the field. All of the participants stated how useful and mind-opening the visit was for them, considering their future work possibilities. A short interview with one of the participants has been uploaded at the YouTube channel of the PreMETS project. Unfortunately, not all of the pilot's participants could make it to the visit, as the varying and different schedules transferred the visit's date – when some of the students had already left for their home towns in other places, or workers could not make it due to their work obligations. Photos of our visit are included at the end of this report.

4.4 Mentorship and other activities

As already mentioned above, both local and international mentors and trainers from the pre-pilot phase were ready at all times during the WBL Pilot's 2 implementation to support learners with their questions independently, or for a discussion regarding the remote outgoing virtual secondments.

Pilot-specific entrepreneurial challenge: This task took place right after the pilot's visit to the Port of Piraeus. With students having already attained a good understanding of Predictive Maintenance on a theoretical level, and after an excellent display of the maritime operations physical location, a comprehensive discussion with the port officials that expanded the scope by analyzing the external environment (the recent supply chain crisis during the COVID era, the repercussions of the recent geopolitical events that reduced the passage of ships through the Suez canal, which deeply affects the port of Piraeus, the challenges of connecting with the national electricity grid for the establishment of facilities for the upcoming obligatory "cold-ironing" in EU ports etc. Under the guidelines and the design provided by YET and EITM, the local trainers of CERTH (with the support of pre-pilot learners from UPRC) provided the students with a task to identify sectoral issues, to define the problems faced and guided them in coming up with an alternative, novel business model – many of its aspects could even be adapted in current business models – that would enhance the company's strengths, overcome its current problems/deficiencies and adapt to a sensitive and ever-changing business environment.

5. Outcomes and certification

The successful completion of the micro-courses by the 25 participants of WBL pilot 2 – PM in maritime operation resulted in the following outcomes:

- 25 certified learners with a strong first background in digital, resilient and sustainable Predictive Maintenance models. This is directly related to the EU's strategic goal of providing its current and future workforce with innovative teaching and learning methodologies that are supported by digital technologies to better prepare them for the challenges that Industry 4.0 brings. The pilot provided the next generation of workforce (most of our participants were students) that is about to enter the job market with a firm grasp of the necessary digital and green skills to adapt to the current EU policies for decarbonisation through energy and primary resources usage efficiency, to which Predictive Maintenance is of crucial importance.
- The certification of the learners means that each and every one of them understood the foundational knowledge of maintenance strategies (and why PM is the future), the necessary technical skills required, and the role of data analytics and machine learning. It also means understanding the industrial equipment and systems (in order to know what to monitor and what potential failures to expect), sharpening their problem solving and decision making skills and working in teams through related workshops and virtual secondments, and understanding the business aspect of PM together with the technical one; not only what it means to the equipment, but also what it means to business.

- The PreMETS learning curriculum, together with the workshops, the on-site visit to the port of Piraeus and the certification that was provided to the 25 learners of the pilot is a well-integrated mix of technical knowledge, analytical abilities' practice, and a first-hand observation of practical application of PM where it actually happens. It is the first step for those interested in pursuing a relative career and cover the emerging professional needs of the maritime transport sector, as well as others due to its cross-sectoral nature. It is also a great opportunity for existing workforce to expand their knowledge and evolve, as some of our participants admitted.
- Impact on the maritime transport sector: Applying Predictive Maintenance in maritime transport, especially in ports, has the potential to improve operations, reduce costs and enhance safety by reducing accidents, as we had the opportunity to observe and listen directly from the port officials. Based on their experience and expertise, they stressed how important it is to mitigate equipment downtime, especially during the post-COVID era where ports are working close to the maximum of their operational capabilities, which makes every minute count. The use of sensors, data analytics and machine learning to anticipate equipment failures before they occur are crucial for minimizing unplanned downtime, especially in equipment such as port cranes, conveyor belts, pumps and loading/unloading systems.

Consequentially, PM in maritime transport operations improves the supply chain efficiency by securing less delays, it enhances the safety of the personnel and prevents the damage of cargo in case of equipment failure, and provides environmental benefits by reducing emissions and preventing potential environmental pollution (e.g. by oil leaks). All of the above also translate into financial benefits in many forms: from cutting maintenance costs to smarter allocation of resources to avoiding liability claims, reducing insurance premiums and aligning with the EU digital and environmental policies.

6. Stakeholders' collaboration

The successful implementation of the pilot is largely owed to the high-level, harmonic cooperation between the partners of the consortium. From its beginning till the recent completion of the WBL pilots, the PreMETS project has had a well-defined and professional consortium management and coordination process. It put a strong emphasis on teamwork, especially since a great part of our pilot activities was done online, with the risk of disengagement always present in such projects. We successfully concluded both digital and physical elements thanks to a number of factors; firstly, the experience of previous cooperation between some of the partners was important, as it provided for seamless communication and trust during the execution of our tasks. Secondly, a strong team-building and collegial, helpful attitude was prevalent during the implementation of the pilot by the coordinator and the WP leader, not only in social activities during our in-person events but also through informal social interaction. Thirdly, all partners have professionally complied with the high-level, standardized set of methods of communication and delivery in the deadlines provided.

For the successful implementation of the pilot, there has been close collaboration with the industry, especially in organizing the visit to the port of Piraeus. For the purpose of recruiting the participants for the pilot, we came

in contact with a number of logistics and maritime operations-related businesses, and some of them expressed their will in providing us with some of their employees to participate in it. During the aforementioned Thessaloniki International Fair (TIF) in September, a number of entrepreneurs that visited the Pavillion that hosted the representatives of PreMETS expressed their interest in the project and the digital platform, seeing an upskilling opportunity for their employees as well. The project representatives provided them with further information about registration on the website and enrolling in the courses provided.

With regards to the public sector and local authorities, representatives from the consortium had the opportunity to come in contact with a number of ministers, parliament members both from the government and opposition parties, as well as regional and municipal officials from Central Macedonia during the TIF between 6-14 of September. It was a great opportunity to inform them about the project as a whole, and more specifically about the latest milestone that this pilot represents. Their interest in projects that enhance the digital and green skills of the workforce provide an opportunity for wider state attention in the next steps of the project, even after the conclusion of the project that will have the digital platform and the micro-credential certification outcomes continue to exist for the benefit of those interested in Predictive Maintenance.

7. Evaluation

The evaluation of the WBL Pilot 2 actions was systematically conducted in alignment with the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in the official project report. This evaluation aimed to measure not only the immediate outputs of the pilot but also its broader contribution to educational innovation, skills development, and industry-academia collaboration. By linking the pilot's outcomes to the project's formal KPIs, we ensured that the assessment was structured and comparable across other pilots and activities within the project.

The evaluation process combined quantitative indicators (such as the number of participants engaged, courses developed, and mobility activities implemented) with qualitative measures capturing the effectiveness of the learning experience, stakeholder satisfaction, and the relevance of acquired skills to labor market needs. Special attention was given to the pedagogical innovations tested in the pilot, including blended learning, micro-credentials, and collaborative, student-centered approaches, which were designed to increase engagement and ensure that the training was closely aligned with industry demands.

The evaluation also addressed the project's contribution to key European Commission policy priorities, including the European Green Deal, the digital transition, and the promotion of inclusive and sustainable education. It assessed how the pilot strengthened links between education, research, and innovation, facilitated employability, and supported regional and cross-border cooperation. The results confirmed that the pilot achieved high impact in knowledge transfer, digital upskilling, and stakeholder collaboration, creating a replicable model for future WBL initiatives.

The results derived are presented below.

Type of project, thematic areas and types of activities.

- New innovative curricula/educational methods/development of training courses: **YES**
- VET teachers/trainers professional development: **YES**

Education levels

- Higher education: **YES**
- Adult education: **YES**
- Vocational training: **YES**

EQF levels

- Second cycle / Master's or equivalent level (ISCED-7) : **YES**
- Post-secondary non-tertiary education (ISCED-4) : **YES**

Academic fields

- Internet of Things: **YES**
- Maritime and coastal management: **YES**
- Digital transformation: **YES**
- Big data
- Circular economy: **YES**

Pedagogies

- Pedagogies: **YES**
- Micro-credential courses: **YES**
- Collaborative learning: **YES**
- Blended learning: **YES**
- Student centered learning: **YES**
- Entrepreneurship education: **YES**
- Multi-disciplinary or cross-disciplinary education: **YES**

Target groups

- Students: **YES**
- Researchers: **YES**
- Other (s)
- Academic staff
- Staff of enterprises: **YES**

Sectors (only for ALLIANCES FOR INNOVATION actions)

- Mobility-transport-Automotive: **YES**
- Electronics
- Digital: **YES**

Mobility Activities

- Yes

Type of mobility

- Physical mobility: **YES**

- Virtual mobility: **YES**

Number of persons involved in mobility/virtual mobility

- 25

Does the project contribute to any of the EU Commission political priorities?

- A European Green Deal - Climate change: **YES**
- A European Green Deal - Sustainable Europe investment plan: **YES**
- A Europe fit for the digital age - The digital age: **YES**
- An economy that works for people - Social fairness and prosperity: **YES**
- A Europe fit for the digital age - Empowering people through education and skills: **YES**
- An economy that works for people - Supporting small business: **YES**

Does the project address inclusion and diversity?

- Yes

Does the project address participation and civic engagement?

- Yes

Is the project focused on regional cooperation i.e. cooperation between countries in a region of the world (only for CB-VET and CB-HE actions)?

- Yes

Output, result and impact indicators

- Development of schemes that facilitate the employability of graduates: **YES**
- Contribution to creation of regional HE area (facilitate national and cross-border: **YES**
- recognition, support mobility of teachers, learners and workers) : **YES**
- Strengthening of links between education, research and innovation: **YES**
- Contribution to the reform of higher education policies that respond to societal and labour market needs: **YES**

Cooperation agreements with stakeholders:

- Education institutions not involved in the project
- Local authorities
- Research institutions
- Associations, civil society organisations and NGOs
- Private sector
- Public sector
- Social enterprises

Do you consider that the project has improved the awareness and the perception of the EU's support in the areas addressed by Erasmus+ in (one or more) third?

- Yes

Do you consider that your organisations/institutions have developed high-quality practices as a result of the participation in this project?

- Yes

Number of new courses:

- 14

Number of new study programmes:

- 2

Number of persons reached:

- 25 (13 female, 12 male)

Number of students/university staff reached

- 15

8. Annex A: Photos from the on-site visit to PCT

